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REVIEW OF THE JOB SEARCH WORKSHOP PROGRAM

CITIZENSHIP AND IMMIGRATION CANADA, ONTARIO REGION

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1. Executive Summary

The objectives of this review of the Job Search Workshop Program (JSW) were to assess JSW as it is currently delivered across Ontario, and to make recommendations for improving the delivery of the program.

JSW is an Ontario-wide program funded by Citizenship and Immigration Canada since 1997, and aims to help newcomers find jobs by orienting them to the Canadian labour market.

For the review, RealWorld Systems collected information from many different perspectives, including the research literature, JSW agencies, clients, employment experts, and previous assessments of the program.

The main findings were:

- JSW directly addresses the most important difficulty faced by immigrants to Canada, as well as one of the primary outcomes of Canada's immigration policy – integration into the labour market.
- The JSW service model (providing workshops in independent job search techniques to newcomers) is supported by research and community needs. However, the current curriculum and activities focus on general orientation to the job market, which has limited effectiveness.
- JSW is provided by agencies across Ontario, providing a service infrastructure with many committed and skilled staff.
- JSW is not being defined or delivered consistently across the province, and staff qualifications and program activities vary widely.
- Performance data are not consistent with JSW's goals, data collection is spotty and unreliable, and the quality of the data is not adequate for monitoring or improving the program.

The report makes five recommendations for the improvement of the Job Search Workshop program:

1. **Define JSW's overall program goal and learning outcomes, anchoring them to the COIA logic model and ensuring consistency throughout the province.**

Proposed Goal – *Newcomers have the skills to find and apply for suitable employment*

Proposed Learning Outcomes – *At the end of a JSW program, students should demonstrate proficiency at:*

- *Matching their employment goals, skills, education and experience to appropriate Canadian occupations*
 - *Writing resumes and cover letters that communicate their skills, education and experience in relation to their desired employment*
 - *Communicating their suitability for a desired position in a job interview*
 - *Conducting independent job searches tied to their employment goals*
2. **Revise JSW curriculum, materials and program models to achieve the goal and learning outcomes.** This will involve developing and testing an effective curriculum and other resources based on adult education principles, and incorporating the best practices from current JSW programs.
 3. **When possible, provide JSW curriculum and teaching aids online for self-directed learners.** Much of JSW's curriculum will include relevant pre-arrival information, and would help internationally trained professionals to prepare for an independent job search in Canada. In fact, face-to-face Job Search Workshops can test and refine content that can be posted online for independent learners.
 4. **Improve information and referral links between JSW and relevant programs and services.** This will require a better intake and assessment process to ensure that eligible newcomers are referred to JSW, and that they are referred to external programs (such as career bridging or professional certifications) when appropriate.
 5. **Revise performance measures to support JSW's goal and learning outcomes, and ensure that they are collected and analysed appropriately.** In many cases, it will be more cost effective to collect fewer measures more accurately. The cost of high quality data collection should be funded by CIC.

2. Background

The Job Search Workshop Program (JSW) is one of the many services provided by Citizenship and Immigration Canada (CIC) to help newly arrived permanent residents settle, adapt and integrate into Canadian society. JSW was first piloted in 1994 and became an Ontario-wide program in 1997. Job Search Workshops are 3 to 4 days long, with additional follow-up support, and they attempt to teach basic skills and practices related to obtaining employment in Canada.

JSW is available in both French and English, and is offered at various times of the day and week to ensure accessibility. The program served almost 9,000 clients in 2005/6, and is delivered by 44 community agencies across Ontario. It was last evaluated in 2001.

Citizenship and Immigration Canada, Ontario Region, will be going through a number of major changes over the next few years; specifically sharing the delivery of settlement services with the provincial government through the Canada-Ontario Immigration Agreement, and renegotiating mandates with federal departments as responsibilities and departments are redefined. This review was an opportunity to assess JSW in the context of these broader issues.

3. Methodology

The JSW review collected data from a wide variety of sources to ensure that the final recommendations would incorporate perspectives of key stakeholders and be based on the best possible evidence. The methodology is described in more detail in the Technical Report that was submitted as a companion document to this paper. In brief, it included the following activities:

- Ongoing consultation with the JSW Advisory Committee, which advised on all aspects of the research and provided in-depth feedback to the findings and recommendations. The Committee included representatives from service provider agencies and funders and their names are included in the Appendix.
- Review of relevant background documents regarding Citizenship and Immigration Canada programs, including the 2001 program review of Job Search Workshops, the current transition of programs from CIC to the Ontario government under the

- Canada-Ontario Immigration Agreement, and other policy and research papers published on government sites and settlement.org.
- Review of the international research literature on success factors and effective service models relating to job finding, particularly for immigrants. The literature review is included in the Technical Report.
 - Review of JSW service statistics, comparing current and past data regarding numbers of clients served in regions across Ontario, and their success rates where available.
 - Interviews with employment experts recommended by members of the JSW Advisory Committee (their names are included in the Appendix). The interviews tested hypotheses as they emerged from the other data sources, and ensured that our assumptions were questioned, challenged and examined at each stage of the analysis.
 - Survey of service provider organizations delivering JSW across Ontario. They were surveyed at two points in March and April; via a 2-page questionnaire at the annual conference of JSW facilitators, and via a 16-page questionnaire sent to all agencies which elicited an 81% response rate. The survey results are included in the Technical Report.
 - Site visits to four agencies that were selected based on their reputation for delivering effective JSW programs (as identified in interviews and a preliminary consultation with the JSW Advisory Committee), as well as representing different regions in Ontario. The reputational approach is useful in program reviews in which reliable outcome data are not available, because one can assume that the agencies are more likely to be effective than the average. Reviewers can get a feel for the 'state of the art' in program delivery. In addition, agencies that have been chosen based on a good reputation (as opposed to being selected randomly) tend to be more willing to share information about problems and challenges that they are facing.

4. Summary of Findings

Detailed results from the literature review, agency survey, statistical analysis and so on are included in the companion Technical Report. The main findings below are the major points that emerged from our investigations, and that drive the report's recommendations.

- a. *JSW directly addresses the most important difficulty faced by immigrants to Canada, as well as one of the primary outcomes for Canada's immigration policy – integration into the labour market.*

The Canadian government has identified immigration as a fundamental strategy to address Canada's human capital requirements over the next few decades¹.

Newcomers are expected to fill the looming labour market gaps that will result from an aging population, and to contribute to a healthy, growing knowledge-based economy².

The Canada-Ontario Immigration Agreement has identified three outcomes explicitly related to employment:

- Newcomers have the skills to find and apply for employment (short term)
- Newcomers are linked to local labour markets (short term)
- Newcomers have paid work consistent with their education, skills and experience (intermediate outcome)

JSW addresses all three to some extent, but is directly aimed at the first outcome – helping newcomers obtain the skills to find and apply for employment.

¹ Alboim N and McIsaac E. 2007. Making the connections: Ottawa's role in immigrant employment. IRPP Choices. 13(3). Retrieved from <http://www.irpp.org/choices/archive/vol13no3.pdf> [All web references in this report were tested between May 23-27, 2007]

² According to a Human Resources Development Report on the knowledge economy, "immigrants are expected to account for 100 per cent of Canada's net labour force growth by 2011 and 100 per cent of net population growth by 2031." Retrieved from <http://www1.sdc.gc.ca/sl-ca/infokit/imm.shtml>

Help is certainly needed. Although Canada is successfully attracting large numbers of educated and skilled immigrants³, recent research suggests that newcomers are finding it increasingly difficult to integrate fully into Canada's labour market.

According to a new study by Statistics Canada⁴, the most important difficulty reported by new immigrants is the challenge of obtaining an adequate job. "Almost half (45%) of economic immigrants said finding employment was the most important difficulty they faced, while this was the case for 22% and 26% of family class immigrants and refugees respectively." (The second most important difficulty was learning a new language.)

Immigrants report many types of difficulties in job finding (see table below). The list is familiar to anyone who has worked in the settlement sector: The most frequently reported barrier is the lack of Canadian experience, followed by the lack of social networks in local job markets, a lack of recognition of foreign qualifications, and so on. "Not knowing how to find a job is reported by only 10%, but is related to most of the other difficulties.

In fact, JSW has the potential to address most of these barriers. For example, the complaint of 'not enough Canadian job experience' can often mean that the prospective employer cannot easily translate the newcomer's skills into a Canadian context. With a well-written resume that explicitly relates the newcomer's background into Canadian equivalents, this barrier can be reduced. The complaint of 'no connections in the job market' can be addressed by teaching newcomers how to identify relevant contacts in their broader social networks and carry out information interviews. JSW can be designed to lessen the impact of each barrier by helping the newcomer to problem-solve or locate relevant resources.

³ Alboim and McIsaac, 2007. "Among permanent residents over the age of 15 who were landed in 2005, 45.9 percent had a university degree. Within the economic class, or skilled-worker category, 79.5 percent of principal applicants had at least one university degree." P3.

⁴ Statistics Canada. Immigrants' perspectives on their first four years in Canada: Highlights from three waves of the Longitudinal Survey of Immigrants to Canada. Canadian Social Trends, April 2007. Retrieved May 1 2007 at <http://www.statcan.ca/english/freepub/11-008-XIE/2007000/pdf/11-008-XIE20070009627.pdf> The table is from page 8 of the report.

Other studies over the last few years have pointed to a disturbing trend. New immigrants and their families, despite being significantly more educated than immigrants in years past, are likely to fall into a period of low income within two years of arrival, and their labour market outcomes are poorer than immigrants from previous decades⁵.

⁵ Statistics Canada 2007. Chronic low income and low-income dynamics among recent immigrants. <http://www.statcan.ca/english/research/11F0019MIE/11F0019MIE2007294.htm>; and Statistics Canada 2005. The deteriorating economic welfare of immigrants and possible causes. <http://www.statcan.ca/english/research/11F0019MIE/11F0019MIE2005262.pdf>

This is an important issue for Ontario, which attracts over half of all of Canada's newcomers - 140,533 in 2005, of whom about 75,000 entered Ontario intending to find employment. The Toronto urban area alone received 43% of the total immigration to Canada.⁶

Figure 1. Percentage of permanent residents by province or territory, 2005⁷

The governments of Ontario and Canada are engaged in developing policies and programs that facilitate the integration of these massive waves of newcomers, to maximize their contribution and lessen the risks of creating disaffected, impoverished new communities.

- b. *The JSW service model (providing workshops in independent job search techniques to newcomers) is supported by research and community needs. However, JSW's current curriculum and activities focus on general orientation to the job market, which has limited effectiveness.*

⁶ CIC Facts and Figures 2005, <http://www.cic.gc.ca/english/pub/facts2005/index.html>

⁷ CIC Facts and Figures 2005, <http://www.cic.gc.ca/english/pub/facts2005/permanent/17.html>

JSW was first pilot tested in 1994 as a response to the observation by settlement agencies that newcomers were often unaware of basic elements of a Canadian job search, including the role of resumes, how to apply for jobs, how to understand what an employer was looking for, and so on. The three-day Job Search Workshops were designed to orient newcomers to a wide range of topics, from writing a resume to understanding labour law. Over time, agencies adapted JSW to meet community needs, and expanded the model to include weekends and evenings.

The 'orientation' approach seemed to be an obvious way of helping newcomers figure out how to search for jobs, and it was consistent with the 'information and orientation' role of settlement agencies.

However, the current research literature on successful job searches and routes to employment shows little support for the effectiveness of the general orientation approach. Finding and obtaining jobs is a very complex process, requiring a set of specific skills and behaviours, and orientation does not appear to be an appropriate service model. (See the Technical Report for the literature review.)

Unfortunately, there is little consensus in the literature regarding what is effective. Some highlights of the research are: that social networks are useful in obtaining jobs, but employers appear to use networks differently when hiring professionals versus unskilled workers; that there is little or no evidence that any one job search technique is more effective than others; that the best predictors of successful job searches are the strategy that is used to direct the search and the intensity of the search itself; and that the frequently cited need for Canadian experience may have several components, including the difficulty in translating international experience in terms that Canadian employers can relate to. The overall conclusion that we drew from the research is that this field is really, really complicated, with few evidence-based practice guidelines, and it's no wonder that there is little consensus regarding JSW's curriculum and service activities. (This conclusion, depressing as it sounds, is consistent with recent reviews that RealWorld Systems has carried out regarding employment services for people with disabilities.)

Experts in the field of employment programs for immigrants told us:

- A JSW orientation program can help people pull together a very general resume that will help get a survival job, but will not help professionals or skilled workers obtain appropriate employment
- It is logistically impossible to provide an effective service with the current model. It is a watering down of help. The unintended consequence is to discourage the new internationally trained immigrant.
- Different career paths require different support needs, and employment programs must be able to respond to these needs appropriately.
- Intake and assessment, eligibility and employment readiness must be dealt within the JSW screening process, and require good referral links to appropriate services if clients are not suitable for JSW.

Based on the literature, interviews with experts, and conversations with agencies, we can draw a few conclusions.

- Job seekers must be able to do four things in order to be competent at finding and obtaining suitable work:
 - Match their employment goals, skills, education and experience to appropriate Canadian occupations;
 - Write resumes and cover letters that communicate their skills, education and experience in relation to their desired employment;
 - Communicate their suitability for a desired position in a job interview;
 - Conduct independent job searches using a variety of techniques relevant to their employment goals

These learning outcomes are fully consistent with the mandate of JSW.

- A three-day JSW workshop is not sufficient to equip most clients with all of the skills that they need to carry out effective independent job searches. However, it may be enough to lay the groundwork by teaching concepts and techniques for local job searches, by helping clients to develop a basic resume and cover letter, and by practicing interview skills.
- For skilled workers and professionals, finding and obtaining suitable employment is a complex process that probably requires exposure to people who have local knowledge about the specific occupations. This might include

internships, formal or informal mentorships, interactions with workers in the same industry and so on. It is unreasonable to expect JSW staff to know all of the complexities of every profession, and JSW may need to teach clients how to find these relationships for themselves.

- An essential step in a successful job search is to define feasible employment goals, which requires that jobseekers match their skills, experience and qualifications with their desired occupations. This career exploration activity is especially important for internationally trained immigrants, since their job qualifications may need to be upgraded or else clearly explained to Canadian employers using the correct jargon. The career exploration stage is not adequately addressed in most JSW programs. Without it, internationally trained immigrants are unlikely to properly target their job search, and may develop unrealistic or inappropriate goals.

- c. *JSW is provided by agencies across Ontario, providing a service infrastructure with many committed and skilled staff.*

JSW programs are located in 44 agencies all over Ontario, most of which provide a range of settlement services to immigrants and refugees, and 80% of which have delivered JSW for at least 5 years. Staff training and development is provided centrally by COSTI and OCASI.

JSW programs are designed to be flexible, and the lack of formality and structure enables agencies to respond to different community needs. Many JSW providers have customized their programs to reach out to specific groups, such as women, engineers, youth and so on. JSW needs flexibility to deal with different service contexts, since Ontario regions vary widely in the number and type of services that can serve clients. For example, some agencies take advantage of Toronto's rich referral network to specialize in certain aspects of job search skills, referring clients out for other kinds of job search assistance.

Some JSW programs have close referral links with other community services, and several, especially in Ottawa, involve partnerships and resource-sharing between other immigrant-serving agencies.

In our site visits, we saw some examples of excellent facilitation and training on core employment skills. In fact, one of the writers of this report, a rehabilitation psychologist, learned some useful tips that she passed on to family members. The students in those workshops spoke forcefully in support of the usefulness of the program, and several said that they now understand why their previous job searches had been unsuccessful.

- d. *JSW is not being defined or delivered consistently across the province, and staff qualifications and program activities vary widely.*

The JSW program was set up as a response to an urgent need for job search assistance from immigrants in the early 1990s. It was a creative extension to the Immigrant Settlement and Adaptation Program (ISAP), and was not defined and formalized as a separate program.

Fortunately, JSW agencies across the province have a high degree of consensus regarding program priorities and learning outcomes. In their responses to this survey question – “What are the top 2 or 3 things a student needs to do successfully at the end of the workshop in order for your agency to conclude that the workshop has been successful?” – 80% fit into one of four skill areas: developing a targeted resume and cover letter; participating effectively in a job interview; conducting an independent job search; and knowing their own strengths, weaknesses and transferrable skills.

In addition, the core learning outcomes identified by the JSW agencies are fully consistent with its outcome as stated in the logic model of the Canada-Ontario Immigration Agreement: *Newcomers have the skills to find and apply for employment.*

Even though JSW has a high degree of informal consensus on goal and outcomes, the lack of formality means that it has not standardized its curriculum, activities or learning objectives. The JSW Manual, disseminated to every agency providing JSW, is a collection of suggested exercises and activities rather than a defined curriculum. It does not set desired outcomes or prioritize activities. According to the agency survey, this lack of consistency is reflected in the ways that JSW is delivered throughout Ontario. Our strong impression based on interviews and site

visits is that many agencies are doing good work, and many clients are benefitting from JSW, but positive results are based on the 'common sense' of skilled providers rather than evidence-based programming.

We heard of several instances in which JSW facilitators gave inaccurate information to students, or spent most of the workshops lecturing rather than engaging students in interactive exercises, or selected exercises that did not address the core learning outcomes. It is unreasonable to expect new and untrained facilitators to develop effective programs on their own, and given the lack of consistency and clarity we suspect there are many ineffective programs. At the same time, we want to acknowledge the commitment of many skilled staff who consciously reject higher-paid jobs in favour of working with newcomers in difficult circumstances.

We heard from our expert interviews, site visits and the agency survey that:

- JSW contracts from CIC are not consistent across regions, and include different activities (for example, employment plans are required in some JSW contracts but not in others).
- Some JSW agencies provide inaccurate or inadequate referral information to clients. Employment services and community programs change constantly, but many JSW agencies do not keep up with the referral networks and resources. Some JSW programs compete with or duplicate other services (such as JobConnect) rather than working productively with them. Others work closely with sister agencies like JobConnect, customizing their services to maximize their joint impact.
- Some 'non-JSW' supports are essential for making JSW effective in helping clients to search for jobs, particularly internet-connected computers, printers and telephones. In some cases these resources are available through Employment Resource Centres located close to the JSW program, but if not, they need to be provided in some other way.
- Some agencies use funding from external sources (like donations) to pay for client supports that are not eligible under CIC but that they believe are essential, including childcare, transportation and snacks.

- There are not enough financial resources to cover all of the key components of JSW (e.g., helping students develop effective resumes), so agencies make different tradeoffs based on their assessment of priorities.
- The screening procedures are inconsistent; in some cases programs accept students with low English/ French skills, while others restrict participation to students with LINC level 4 or above.

According to several of the people we interviewed, there is high staff turnover of JSW facilitators in many agencies. COSTI reports that over 50% of participants in JSW training are new every year, a combination of turnover and expansion of JSW. In our own interviews and site visits, we heard that staff experience and qualifications varied widely. In our site visits we saw experienced and committed facilitators who worked skillfully with their groups and who clearly worked many hours of overtime; we also heard about staff with limited experience and training in the field of job development and adult education. Senior staff at the agencies we visited pointed out that effective Job Search Workshops require facilitators who understand the subtleties of the Ontario labour market and can give good advice to skilled workers and professionals. The annual JSW staff development sessions (as acknowledged by COSTI), are not in-depth enough to turn someone into a skilled educator with comprehensive knowledge of the Canadian labour market.

The problem of staff capacity is difficult to address, since better training, more highly qualified staff and lowered turnover would all require significantly higher costs. This is an ongoing problem within the settlement sector, and not restricted to JSW. We heard in several interviews that settlement agencies often hire recently arrived internationally trained professionals with strong backgrounds in counseling and social services, but who may not have much experience in negotiating the Canadian labour market. When offered a job that pays a higher salary, generally outside the settlement sector, they tend to leave.

- e. Performance data are not consistent with JSW's goals, data collection is spotty and unreliable, and the quality of the data is not adequate for monitoring or improving the program.*

As stated above, JSW does not have formal or consistent goals and outcomes. It is not surprising then that performance measures have not been designed to be valid, reliable, useful and cost effective indicators of JSW outcomes. JSW service statistics include the number of clients who obtained employment within three months after concluding the workshop; in fact, this is not a useful indicator for several reasons that are summarized in the literature review.

In summary, the 3-month measure should, in our opinion, not be whether the JSW client is currently in a job, but rather whether the client has obtained relevant job interviews and job offers. The goal of the JSW is for newcomers to have the skills to find and apply for jobs. Using the wrong performance indicator leads to unrealistic client expectations and confusion about what to emphasize in the program. For example, if the desired outcome is simply to obtain work, as clients are told, then job developers or placement agencies would be a more suitable intervention than workshops.

In our judgement, CIC funding for JSW does not recognize the costs of collecting, auditing and analyzing reliable performance data. This is reflected in the poor quality of the data at all levels.

Some of the problems with JSW data include:

- Data are collected inconsistently; the data definitions are unclear, and/or agencies have interpreted them differently. For example, 'survival jobs' have several meanings depending on the agency.
- Some agencies have dedicated significant resources to collecting and quality-checking data, often funded by non-CIC sources, while others have not. The data quality varies so widely that it is impossible to compare the results between agencies. (Staff of one agency said that they have no funding to track outcomes, but that clients are encouraged to drop in and tell staff when they have located a job.)
- The combined agency data have not been checked or cleaned for quality. For example, one agency stated that five clients attended a workshop and ten of them completed it successfully. These obviously flawed data result in misleading service statistics.

- The measures themselves create perverse incentives (in other words, they discourage service providers from doing the right things). Current measures discourage agencies from making appropriate external referrals, encourage agencies to promote ‘survival jobs’, and encourage them to compete with other community services even when it does not benefit their clients.

All of these limitations make us cautious about reporting on service statistics. However, even with those cautions, there are some interesting patterns in the statistics that are worth examining:

- There seems to be an 11% decrease in new JSW clients from two years ago (9,827 to 8,756). This decrease was observed by several agencies, and has led to suspicions that clients are selecting other services in preference to JSW.
- JSW agencies report that they did follow-up surveys on 7,786 clients (representing 91% of clients that completed workshops in 2005/06. 51% of those surveyed were employed 3 months after completing workshops. (Many may have been employed before starting the workshop.)
- Of these employed clients, 47% were employed in ‘survival jobs’. Of those who found survival jobs, 91% had post-secondary education or higher. Of the total number of clients who reported being employed after the JSW workshop, 41% considered that employment to be in a field related to their experience/skills.

We have reservations about the accuracy of these data, based on asking agencies about their data collection processes. Assuming they were accurate though, it looks like there is, at most, a 20% success rate of immigrants obtaining work in a field related to their experience/skills three months after completing JSW (41% of 51%).

Statistics Canada has collected information on job-finding success in the general population of Canadian immigrants, which provides some context. According to Statistics Canada, “The vast majority (80%) of prime working-age immigrants found employment during their first two years in Canada, and most worked for more than one year. Of those who found employment, 42% obtained a job in their

intended occupation. This was the case for about half (48%) of principal applicants in the skilled worker category.”⁸ This type of information may be useful as a baseline in the future, since we can assume that about 34% of immigrants will be employed in their intended occupation within 2 years of entry.

However, we don’t know if the JSW results above are good or not, even if they are accurate. JSW clients may be less competent at job-finding than the general population of immigrants sampled by Statistics Canada or more competent (since they found JSW). These kinds of statistics by themselves tell us very little, and better data are needed.

5. Recommendations

The picture of the Job Search Workshop program described above is somewhat gloomy. The good news is that it is possible to make a significant improvement in the effectiveness of the program, and benefit a far wider range of clients than currently have access to it.

We have five recommendations, which taken together will lead to a significantly different way of delivering Job Search Workshops. For two case scenarios showing how JSW may look in the future, see the Appendix.

Recommendation 1: Define the Job Search Workshop Program’s overall goal and learning outcomes, anchoring them to the COIA logic model and ensuring consistency throughout the province.

Proposed Goal – Newcomers have the skills to find and apply for suitable employment.

Proposed Learning Outcomes – At the end of a JSW program, students should demonstrate proficiency at:

- *Matching their employment goals, skills, education and experience to appropriate Canadian occupations*

⁸ Statistics Canada 2003. From Longitudinal Survey of Immigrants to Canada: Progress and Challenges of New Immigrants in the Workforce. <http://www.statcan.ca/english/freepub/89-615-XIE/89-615-XIE2005001.pdf>, pg 6.

- *Writing resumes and cover letters that communicate their skills, education and experience in relation to their desired employment*
- *Communicating their suitability for a desired position in a job interview*
- *Conducting independent job searches tied to their employment goals*

As a first step towards increasing its effectiveness, the Job Search Workshop Program should state clear goals and outcomes related to the COIA logic model. The proposed goal is based on two outcomes from the logic model: *Newcomers have the skills to find and apply for employment* (short term outcome), and *Newcomers have paid work consistent with their education, skills and experience* (intermediate outcome, and captured in 'suitable employment').

The goal should be included in future CIC contracts, and should guide the development of revised performance measures.

Note that JSW's goal addresses the '*skills for finding and applying suitable employment*', and does not refer to actually obtaining a job. This may seem subtle, but is crucial for JSW. Newcomers need to learn how to look for appropriate work – not only for their first job in Canada, but at intervals for the rest of their working lives.

If the outcome is merely employment, the most efficient intervention is to provide clients with a job developer, and/or encourage them to accept any low-level job that comes along. In many cases, though, the appropriate outcome of a JSW program is that a client goes back for further training or certification. So JSW should enable newcomers to figure out what kind of job is relevant to their long term employment goals, and when they are ready to apply, how to communicate their qualifications to potential employers in a way that will enable them to compete effectively with native-born Canadians.

The four learning outcomes below will probably require further discussion before being finalized. The proposed outcomes stipulate that at the end of a JSW program, students should demonstrate proficiency at four core skills. Further work is required to assess what level of proficiency should be expected, and whether JSW is able to deliver an acceptable level with the resources available to it.

The learning outcomes are based on adult education principles, and assume that JSW is primarily an adult education program rather than a general orientation. Some orientation is necessary in any educational program, but it is not an end in itself.

Outcomes allow learners to decide whether the program is relevant to their needs, and it also enables service providers to focus on the educational elements that are most important.

According to our research, there are four core skills that are necessary to enable newcomers to find and apply for suitable employment:

- *Matching their employment goals, skills, education and experience to appropriate Canadian occupations*

This first skill provides a base for all of the other activities of JSW. Without this skill, newcomers will not be able to set appropriate employment targets for themselves. They need to understand how their qualifications and experience suit them for jobs in Canada, and whether they need additional training or credentials. In some cases, they will need to go back to school in order to attain their goals; in most cases, they will probably have to make some adjustments in their immediate employment objectives based on the realities of the local labour market. This process requires career exploration and planning, and can rarely be completed in a day or two.

- *Writing resumes and cover letters that communicate their skills, education and experience in relation to their desired employment*

Newcomers' resumes and cover letters must translate what the newcomer can do, in terms that the Canadian employer can understand. Most employers can translate the relevance of Canadian work experience to their own needs, but have no context for international experience.

The European Union, in trying to encourage labour mobility throughout Europe, has found that differences in job vocabulary and school systems between member nations present serious barriers to workers who cross borders looking for work. The EU has introduced a major initiative, the Europass CV⁹, that translates skills, experience and qualifications into a

⁹ For information about the Europass, see the companion Technical Report or <http://europass.cedefop.europa.eu/europass/>

common format that can be understood by employers all over Europe. They have also introduced a credential translation service and standards for describing language fluency. Canada has no such program, but the problem is the same. JSW needs to help newcomers explain, in a resume and cover letter, how their qualifications fit their desired occupation. Newcomers cannot expect Canadian employers to do the translation themselves.

- *Communicating their suitability for a desired position in a job interview*

Job interviews are complex interactions that involve many subtle social judgments. Newcomers who do not know ‘interview etiquette’, especially if they are not completely fluent in the interviewer’s language, may come across poorly even if they can describe their qualifications well. Interviews are stressful situations. JSW needs to help newcomers become comfortable and effective in a job interview, which probably requires practice and role playing.

- *Conducting independent job searches tied to their employment goals*

The research on job-finding, as summarized in the findings above, state that successful searches are based on an appropriate strategy for the desired employment goal, combined with the use of many different approaches.

Some newcomers may find certain important job search techniques culturally alien. For example, one employment expert told us that Chinese newcomers were highly reluctant to tap their social networks until networking was described as ‘doing research’. Asking people for favours, according to his Chinese colleagues, meant that they were signaling a lower social status. JSW needs to teach job search skills in ways and using vocabulary that are acceptable to its clients.

Several informants in this study pointed out that newcomers may need encouragement and emotional support from JSW groups in order to build their self-confidence for job searches and interviews.

The four proposed learning outcomes may need revision by educational experts during the development of a revised JSW curriculum to ensure that they are feasible within the resources of JSW.

Each learning outcome should be associated with clear, precise, achievable objectives, with assessment criteria so that JSW programs can track whether their approaches are successful.

Recommendation 2: Revise JSW curriculum, materials and program models to achieve the goal and learning outcomes.

Once the goal and outcomes have been defined, JSW needs a revised curriculum, delivery models and resources to achieve them.

The challenge will be to define some standard elements that must be included in all Job Search Workshops, as well as some elements that can be customized for individual regions or communities.

Some possible approaches that could be considered include:

- Revise the JSW Manual based on adult education principles to emphasize content and activities that lead directly to the learning outcomes, and provide clarity on compulsory versus optional elements.
- Divide JSW into at least two modules:
 - Career exploration and planning (leading to referrals to education/bridging/language programs, or job search), since it generally requires extensive homework and reflection, especially for professionals and skilled workers. This module may require 2 or 3 days in itself, plus homework assignments.
 - Job search methods/ resume development/ interview practice. This module, or modules, may require 3 or more days spread out over two weeks or more, with homework assignments in between, in which students practice information interviews, learn about different cultural communication styles related to job searches, and locate potential mentors and advisors in their social networks.
- Provide staff specialists in resume development and interview practice who can act as resources to several JSW programs. This is currently being done in LASI WorldSkills in Ottawa and is a promising approach.

- Experiment with job interview practice and role-play activities that can productively engage JSW participants with a wide range of language proficiency. Many newcomers will never be fully fluent in English or French, but will still need to find jobs. They can benefit from practice in a job interview by learning helpful clichés and standard interactions.

It will be difficult to strike the correct balance between rigour and evidence-based interventions on one hand, and flexibility and responsiveness to clients on the other hand. JSW will require ongoing critical review by users, agencies and experts to ensure that it continues to improve, and that it does not become over-rigid or over-flexible.

A revised and more effective curriculum will probably require additional resources. Based on research on employment barriers, as well as interviews with agencies and experts, CIC should consider providing:

- Childcare and transportation costs for clients who require them to access the program, as well as snacks and drinks during long workshop sessions (this has the benefit of making an immediate improvement to the program, and shows a commitment to responding to feedback from agencies)
- Additional staff training and development to build JSW's capacity to provide effective instruction and facilitation, possibly including minimum qualifications and a certification process for JSW counsellors to ensure that clients are receiving accurate and updated information
- Possibly additional staffing for one-to-one assistance on resumes and career exploration – the staff may be used to recruit volunteers or mentors rather than giving the assistance directly

Recommendation 3: When possible, provide JSW curriculum and teaching aids online for self-directed learners.

Much of JSW's curriculum will include relevant pre-arrival information, and would help internationally trained professionals to prepare for an independent job search in Canada while completing the final stages of immigration to Canada. Face-to-face Job

Search Workshops can test and refine content that can be posted online for independent learners. Potential locations would include ontarioimmigration.ca, settlement.org, or cic.gc.ca.

This approach would dramatically increase the impact and cost-effectiveness of JSW, and help to define its niche in the service system. There are about 75,000 newcomers entering Ontario every year looking for work. Only about 9,000 of them enroll in JSW. JSW can be a laboratory that locates the best employment resources, customizes them for newcomers when necessary, tests them with immigrants, and then disseminates them online to benefit self-directed learners inside and outside Canada.

Of course, JSW online resources would have to address the interactive elements of job search skills. For one thing, not everyone can learn from online content, especially if they are not literate in English or French. More seriously, most clients will require some kind of personal interaction or facilitation in order to learn the communication skills that are involved in job search.

To develop effective online tools, JSW would have to divide its elements into three categories:

- a. Content that can be posted on a web site and learned independently, such as job search techniques and information about specific occupations;
- b. Behaviours that must be practiced interactively, in a group or individually, such as interview role-playing;
- c. Products that can be prepared independently but require review and feedback, such as resumes and cover letters.

Content in the first category can (and should) be posted online to be readily available to prospective and current immigrants. The second category may require face to face groups (though in the future, interactive computer training based on video gaming techniques have promise). The third category could be carried out via email, online chat or phone calls. The Canadian Immigration Integration Project (see below) is experimenting with online social networks of newcomers, linking them together in discussion groups to provide group support. By analyzing the components of effective job search skill-building, and experimenting with

various approaches, JSW has the potential to benefit a much wider group of people.

Newcomers who need personal interaction, and who cannot use online self-directed learning, can still benefit indirectly from the online material. The online training can be used to teach JSW instructors, so that the information they present to newcomers is updated and accurate. The online curriculum could have multiple uses – as staff development resources, as pre-arrival information, as self-directed courses, and even as canned presentations that are used by JSW students in one room while the facilitator is providing one-to-one assistance in another.

It is important to note that JSW would not be responsible for developing all or even most of this content. Many organizations are developing resources that could be incorporated into a comprehensive set of learning tools and delivered through JSW. For example, the Canadian Immigration Integration Project (CIIP), sponsored by the Association of Canadian Community Colleges, is offering employment preparation programs to skilled workers bound for Canada and living in China, the Philippines and India. CIIP intends to experiment with online programs such as the one being piloted by the Halifax-based Metropolitan Immigrant Settlement Association¹⁰. JSW should partner with organizations that are already testing these approaches, and consider contributing to objective evaluations of their effectiveness.

Recommendation 4: Improve information and referral links between JSW and relevant programs and services.

Many JSW programs require a better intake and assessment process to ensure that eligible newcomers are referred to JSW, and that they are referred to external programs (such as career bridging or professional certifications) when appropriate.

This recommendation applies to all settlement services and is essentially the first of four strategies of the Canada-Ontario Immigration Agreement: *Develop a flexible,*

¹⁰ See http://www.misa.ns.ca/Employment/new_beginnings_online.htm for a description of the 'New Beginnings Online' program, retrieved on July 17 2007.

coordinated system of settlement services with strong linkages and clear pathways to services newcomers need such as language-training, labour-market integration, and social services. It is absolutely essential to provide good assessment and referral services before and possibly after clients attend Job Search Workshops.

JSW, like every other settlement service, must ensure that it is situated within the broader service system, and takes advantage of all of the resources that are available to its clients. In practice, it may not be necessary for JSW staff themselves to assess clients' needs and make external referrals. The sponsoring settlement agencies can, and probably should, provide an intake assessment and referral service before clients enter JSW.

New employment programs are being set up continually by a multitude of players including all levels of government, nonprofits, business groups, universities and colleges, and professional associations. Agencies providing JSW must keep up to date with relevant resources, and refer clients to appropriate programs, including other employment programs that may meet their needs better than JSW. In addition, other agencies serving immigrants should be referring eligible clients to JSW programs. This is an overall systems issue that should be addressed across the Immigrant Settlement and Adaptation Program.

Recommendation 5: Revise performance measures to support JSW's goal and learning outcomes, and ensure that they are collected and analysed appropriately.

Continuous improvement of JSW requires feedback regarding its success in achieving its desired outcomes. However, it is not necessary to collect outcome data from every agency. In most cases, it will be more cost effective to collect fewer measures more accurately.

We recommend that CIC develop a performance measurement system that maximizes the value of data collection. It is expensive to collect, audit, monitor and analyse data, and the current approach is not efficient.

Data collection should be carried out according to good research practice, focusing on measures that will improve service models and using proper sampling techniques. When agencies are expected to collect data, adequate resources should be provided to ensure acceptable quality, including funding, training and monitoring.

Performance measures should provide incentives for good practices, such as providing good assessments and appropriate external referrals, and should minimize perverse incentives that lead to competition for clients and reluctance to work with other agencies.

Following are some specific suggestions for CIC:

- Continue to collect basic service statistics from every agency, including numbers of clients served and the activities that are provided for them, as part of CIC's accountability requirements.
- Request agencies to assess every client for the desired learning outcomes (as described in Recommendation 1, above) at the end of each Job Search Workshop. The assessment might include a rating of the clients' job interview skills, the number of 'cold calls' they have made, and the completeness of their resumes.
- Ensure that regular quality assurance assessments are carried out with each agency to ensure that the JSW curriculum is being taught properly. Assessments would involve (for example) occasional visits from a JSW specialist who would attend sessions, review teaching materials, make suggestions and provide feedback to the agencies. These quality assurance assessments (sometimes called educational audits) could be performed by a central Service Provider Agency, or by a peer review process like the one done by Ontario's community health centres, or by CIC itself. Quality assurance will be a thorny issue for CIC and Service Provider Organizations, since there will be a tension between supportive feedback (which may be ignored by agencies) vs. formal audits reported to CIC (which may be feared and resented). At the very least, CIC must clarify its expectations for JSW activities and put some quality process into place. Note that a good quality assurance process can reduce the need for some forms of data collection, while still increasing the quality of service delivery.
- Carry out detailed follow-up surveys with a carefully chosen sample of agencies to test the effectiveness of the JSW service model. This is a powerful approach to improving JSW, and it is more cost-effective than asking every agency to carry out client follow-ups using brief surveys. For example, an

external research team could do telephone surveys of JSW clients in two or three high-performing agencies before and after implementing the new curriculum. The focus of these mini-studies would be to provide quick feedback to the JSW development efforts, and would lead directly to improvements in the curriculum.

- Finally, if CIC wishes to fund it, agencies can administer a brief survey to clients at a 3-month follow-up which asks them questions like:
 - How many job interviews and offers have you received in the last three months? Have you accepted an offer? Is it in your desired occupation?
 - Are you employed now? Did you have the job before starting the Job Search Workshop? Is it in your desired occupation? Is it a 'survival job'? [define survival job]
 - How effective was the Job Search Workshop?

Note that this survey is probably the least effective performance measure, and the most expensive. If it is desired, we recommend that agencies and CIC evaluate the real costs of collecting these data at an acceptable level of quality, and then evaluate their usefulness, before rolling it out to every JSW service provider.

Performance evaluation is a technical and threatening topic for many agencies, but when it is designed properly, performance measurement systems can support agencies' work, recognize success, and benefit clients. Done poorly, it can be both expensive and misleading for agencies and their funders.

Timing of the Recommendations

The revision, testing and refinement of the JSW curriculum will take several years, and will involve ongoing feedback from JSW staff, experts, clients and other stakeholders. The recommendations should be introduced in two phases over the next three years:

Phase One (2007 – 2008):

- Define JSW's goals and set tentative learning outcomes as proposed in Recommendation 1.

- Provide financial support for elements of JSW that are clearly supported by agency surveys, expert interviews and/or research, including childcare, client transportation, snacks, and access to computers and telephones for job searches.
- Strike a group of agencies and experts to revise the JSW curriculum, working with one or more pilot agencies that have shown leadership in creative and effective programming, and incorporating high quality online materials developed by other organizations.
- Design a streamlined performance measurement system based on desired program outcomes.

Phase Two (2008 – 2010):

- Implement and test revised JSW curriculum in at least two locations (and possibly one international location in collaboration with CIIP), posting relevant components online for self-directed learners.
- Begin rolling out changes to JSW, including staff development and teaching materials.
- Collect feedback from JSW program staff and clients regarding the revised curriculum.
- Implement and test a revised performance measurement system.

Conclusion

The Job Search Workshop Program has an important role in the settlement service system. It addresses one of the most important issues facing immigrants through recognizing their abilities and helping them to adapt to their new environment. It is potentially a cost effective and high-impact program.

The complexity and volatility of the Canadian labour market are challenging for anyone embarking on a career, and especially so for newcomers. JSW will need to incorporate new approaches to adult education and employment programming, and build its capacity to learn from experience, in order to achieve its potential.

Appendix

User Scenarios – How JSW Might Look in the Future

Following are three case examples showing how JSW may function in the future, if the recommendations in this report are implemented. The examples are completely fictitious and take place in 2009.

Laila is a 31 year old woman from Iran, trained and qualified as a professional engineer, who arrived in Ontario six months ago with her husband. She has already obtained official recognition of her educational qualifications from the Professional Engineers of Ontario, because she began preparing for immigration several years ago. Based on her research with Canadian/Ontario government web sites, she knows that it is difficult to find employment in the engineering field; however, she is discouraged by the length of time it is taking her and wants some help in finding an appropriate job.

Laila is an independent learner with excellent English, and has already completed the JSW online lessons. However, she has realized that she needs help to understand the unstated cultural rules about job searches and interviews. When she visits her local settlement agency, she explains her situation, and the intake counselor suggests that she skip the career exploration module of JSW, and just take the interactive job search components – working on her resume, role playing job interviews, and the group interaction and facilitation. Laila agrees.

At her first JSW session, she is surprised by how enjoyable it is to share experiences with other job seekers, and she feels more confident. More important, she understands for the first time why ‘information interviews’ are important - she was too shy to approach acquaintances before, but now realizes that it is a skill she needs to learn. In her group exercises, she practices asking fellow students questions about their work. She also is given a homework assignment to locate someone in her network who knows someone in the engineering field.

At Laila’s second JSW session, she practices job interviews, taking turns role playing; the employer and applicant, and then participates in group discussion after each session. She feels much more confident about interviews in general, but wants more specific guidance related to engineering. The JSW counselor refers her

to a mentoring program for new engineers. By the time she meets her volunteer mentor (she requests a woman engineer since she feels uncomfortable meeting a male stranger), she has a good draft resume, and enough knowledge about the Canadian workforce to take full advantage of her mentor's advice.

Grigory is a 20 year old man from Eastern Europe who arrived in Canada three months ago with his parents. He cannot speak English very well, and he is not sure what career he is interested in. In the short term, he wants to earn money and meet some other young people.

He visits a local settlement agency, and is interviewed by an intake counselor. The counselor suggests that Grigory go to the nearby community college for a vocational assessment, but he insists that he wants a job right away, and will think about schooling later. After some further discussion about his plans and ideas, she refers him to a JSW program. His English skills are just barely good enough to pass the JSW screening.

Grigory is not interested in the career exploration module of JSW. He is invited to join the job search module, which includes resume development and interview practice. On the first day of the program, he participates in a group discussion about how to find jobs in his region. Later in the day, he struggles with a software program that helps him to build a brief resume – he has very little job history so it doesn't take long – and is helped occasionally by a JSW assistant. The software is freely available on the web, and he learns how to use it for future job searches.

The second day, Grigory participates in more group discussions about job finding. It is led by a facilitator who splits the group into two parts – one group goes to the computer room and takes individualized short learning segments from the online JSW materials, and the other group role plays job interviews, taking turns being the employer and the applicant. The groups switch places every hour or two throughout the day.

The third day, Grigory is ready to begin contacting employers. He doesn't need more preparation, since he just wants a basic survival job and he figures he will learn about Canadian job culture on his own. He has decided on bussing in a restaurant, since that may lead to a waiting job with tips in the future. The JSW

group, supported by the counselor, has suggested that he go door to door in a dense restaurant district, handing out his new resume. He is hired within three days.

Grigory knows that if and when he tires of working in a restaurant, he can go back to the community college for a vocational assessment, or back to the settlement agency for another referral.

Murali, age 38, lives in India with his wife and two children and plans to move to Ontario within the next year or two, as soon as his Canadian application for Skilled Worker status is accepted. As part of his application process, he has been encouraged to prepare for employment in Canada by using self-study materials available on government web sites.

Murali goes to www.ontarioimmigration.ca, www.settlement.org and www.cic.gc.ca. Each of those web sites has an easy-to-find link to the same online learning program on how to find an appropriate job. This online course is based on a successful and effective Job Search Workshop program that is updated annually based on feedback and evaluation from users in Canada. Murali is a bit overwhelmed by the length of the program – it will take him several weeks to go through all of the online videos, self-assessment tools and practice exercises.

Fortunately, there is a live chat box on the web site, answered by a real advisor, who helps him select the modules to start with. There is also a lively online discussion group with other JSW students, and Murali is pleased to see that most of them are already living in Canada. The social contact helps him build confidence, and he enjoys reading about his fellow students' experiences in Canada.

Murali goes systematically through the online program. Some of it consists of lessons with quizzes, and others are videos of fake job interviews, with commentary by experts and Canadian employers on what went wrong and what went right in each interview. There are many practice exercises that help him define his skills and experience for career planning and exploration, and eventually he has written a draft resume. He emails it to the JSW site, and in a few days he gets detailed comments on the resume from a JSW staff person located in Ontario.

Later on, he sends his resume to an I.T. professional, also in Ontario, who has been recruited as a volunteer to help newcomers communicate their skills and qualifications in the I.T. industry. Murali plans to submit his resume to a few online job boards that are listed on the JSW site, just in case he can obtain a job before arriving in Canada, but he also knows how to start a job search once he reaches Ontario.

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COIA Logic Model

